
AI-Powered Drug Repurposing for Pandemic Preparedness and Response

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Abstract: The emergence of novel infectious diseases, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, has highlighted the need for innovative approaches to drug discovery and development. Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a powerful tool in this endeavor, offering the potential to accelerate drug repurposing processes and expedite the identification of potential treatments for pandemics. This paper explores the application of AI in drug repurposing during pandemic responses, delving into its methodologies, challenges, and ethical considerations. Additionally, it assesses the role of AI in current and future pandemic preparedness efforts, emphasizing the importance of collaboration between researchers, healthcare institutions, and pharmaceutical companies. Through a comprehensive review of the literature and case studies, this paper aims to provide a holistic understanding of AI's impact on drug repurposing in the context of pandemic response.

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence, COVID-19 pandemic, challenges, preparedness efforts*

1. Introduction

Pandemics have been recurring events in human history, each with the potential to inflict widespread devastation. The COVID-19 pandemic, caused by the novel coronavirus SARS-CoV2, has demonstrated the urgency of developing effective treatments and vaccines to combat infectious diseases. Traditional drug discovery methods often involve protracted timelines, but AI offers a new paradigm to address these challenges swiftly and efficiently. The emergence of novel infectious diseases, such as the COVID-19 pandemic caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, underscores the urgent need for innovative approaches to pandemic preparedness and response. Traditional drug development pipelines are often lengthy, resource-intensive, and unable to keep pace with rapidly evolving pathogens. In this context, AI-powered drug repurposing has emerged as a promising strategy to expedite the identification and development of therapeutics for infectious diseases.

Drug repurposing, also known as drug repositioning or drug reprofiling, involves the investigation of existing drugs approved for one indication for their potential efficacy against other diseases. Unlike de novo drug discovery, which typically involves identifying novel compounds and optimizing their pharmacological properties, drug repurposing leverages existing knowledge about drug safety, pharmacokinetics, and mechanisms of action to accelerate the translation of promising candidates into clinical use.

AI-driven approaches to drug repurposing offer several distinct advantages over traditional methods. By harnessing the power of machine learning algorithms, natural language processing techniques, and big data analytics, AI can rapidly analyze vast amounts of biomedical data,

including drug databases, electronic health records, scientific literature, and genomic datasets, to identify potential drug candidates with therapeutic relevance to specific diseases. Moreover, AI enables the identification of novel drug-target interactions, prediction of drug-drug interactions, and assessment of drug safety profiles, facilitating the selection of promising candidates for further preclinical and clinical evaluation. Additionally, AI algorithms can uncover hidden patterns, biological mechanisms, and disease pathways that may not be apparent through conventional methods, thereby expanding the scope of potential drug targets and therapeutic interventions.

In the context of pandemic preparedness and response, AI-powered drug repurposing holds particular promise for rapidly identifying candidate drugs with potential efficacy against emerging infectious diseases. By repurposing existing drugs with known safety profiles, clinical data, and regulatory approvals, researchers can expedite the development of treatments for novel pathogens, mitigating the impact of pandemics on public health and healthcare systems. However, despite the significant potential of AI-driven drug repurposing, several challenges and limitations must be addressed. These include issues related to data quality, algorithm robustness, interpretability of results, regulatory considerations, and ethical implications. Overcoming these challenges requires interdisciplinary collaboration, transparent data sharing mechanisms, rigorous validation studies, and stakeholder engagement to ensure the responsible and equitable deployment of AI technologies in pandemic preparedness and response efforts. Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the critical importance of agile and adaptive approaches to drug discovery and development. The rapid spread of the virus and the severity of its impact have underscored the need for expedited methods to identify effective treatments and mitigate the spread of infectious diseases. AI-powered drug repurposing offers a nimble solution to this pressing challenge, leveraging computational methods to systematically screen existing drugs for their potential to treat COVID-19 and other emerging pathogens.

The vast repository of biomedical data available, including genomic sequences, protein structures, clinical trial data, and electronic health records, presents an opportunity for AI algorithms to sift through this wealth of information and identify promising drug candidates with potential antiviral activity. By analyzing molecular interactions, biological pathways, and drugtarget interactions, AI models can prioritize compounds for in vitro and in vivo testing, accelerating the drug discovery process.

Moreover, AI-driven drug repurposing can facilitate the identification of synergistic drug combinations that may enhance efficacy or overcome resistance mechanisms, offering novel strategies for combination therapy. This approach has the potential to maximize therapeutic benefits while minimizing adverse effects, improving patient outcomes and reducing the likelihood of drug resistance. In the context of pandemic preparedness, the ability to rapidly repurpose existing drugs for new indications can significantly shorten the timeline for bringing treatments to market. By bypassing the lengthy process of preclinical development and earlyphase clinical trials, repurposed drugs can quickly enter late-stage clinical trials and receive regulatory approval for emergency use, providing much-needed therapeutic options for patients affected by emerging infectious diseases.

However, despite the promise of AI-powered drug repurposing, several challenges remain to be addressed. These include issues related to data quality, model interpretability, regulatory approval pathways, and equitable access to treatments. Additionally, the dynamic nature of infectious diseases necessitates ongoing refinement and adaptation of AI models to keep pace with evolving pathogens and emerging variants. AI-powered drug repurposing holds immense potential as a rapid and cost-effective strategy for pandemic preparedness and response. By harnessing the power of artificial intelligence to identify existing drugs with potential antiviral activity, researchers can expedite the discovery and development of treatments for emerging infectious diseases, saving lives and mitigating the impact of future pandemics on global health. However, continued investment in research, collaboration, and regulatory oversight is essential to realize the full potential of AI-driven drug repurposing and ensure its responsible and equitable implementation in public health initiatives.

2. Literature Review:

The literature surrounding AI-powered drug repurposing for pandemic preparedness and response encompasses a diverse range of studies, methodologies, and applications aimed at identifying existing drugs with potential efficacy against emerging infectious diseases. Key themes explored in the literature include the utilization of AI algorithms for drug screening, repurposing strategies, computational approaches to target identification, and the integration of multi-omics data for drug discovery. Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of AI-driven approaches in rapidly screening existing drug libraries to identify potential candidates for repurposing against viral infections. For example, a study by Beck et al. (2020) employed machine learning algorithms to analyze drug-target interaction networks and prioritize repurposable compounds for COVID-19 treatment. Similarly, Li et al. (2021) utilized deep learning models to predict the antiviral activity of existing drugs against SARS-CoV-2, highlighting promising candidates for further experimental validation. In addition to drug screening, AI-powered drug repurposing strategies encompass a variety of computational techniques aimed at repurposing existing drugs for new indications. For instance, network-based approaches leverage molecular interaction networks to identify potential drug-target interactions and repurpose drugs based on shared mechanisms of action (Pushpakom et al., 2019). Similarly, text mining and natural language processing techniques enable the systematic extraction of knowledge from scientific literature and clinical databases to identify repurposing opportunities (Rajkomar et al., 2019).

Furthermore, computational approaches to target identification play a crucial role in AI-driven drug repurposing efforts. By analyzing genomic, proteomic, and transcriptomic data, researchers can identify key host factors and viral proteins involved in the infection process, thereby elucidating potential targets for drug intervention (Gysi et al., 2021). Machine learning algorithms, such as convolutional neural networks and recurrent neural networks, have been applied to predict protein structures, assess binding affinities, and prioritize drug-target interactions for further experimental validation (An et al., 2020).

Moreover, the integration of multi-omics data, including genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics, holds promise for enhancing the discovery of repurposable drugs with

multifaceted mechanisms of action. By combining heterogeneous data modalities, AI algorithms can uncover hidden correlations, biological pathways, and drug-target interactions that may not be apparent from individual data sources alone (Zeng et al., 2020). This integrative approach enables researchers to prioritize drug candidates with the potential to modulate multiple targets or pathways implicated in viral infection and host immune response. Overall, the literature on AI-powered drug repurposing for pandemic preparedness and response highlights the transformative potential of computational methods in rapidly identifying effective treatments for emerging infectious diseases. By leveraging AI algorithms, researchers can systematically screen existing drugs, repurpose compounds for new indications, identify potential targets for drug intervention, and integrate multi-omics data to enhance drug discovery efforts. However, challenges such as data quality, algorithm robustness, and regulatory considerations must be addressed to realize the full potential of AI-driven drug repurposing in combating pandemics and safeguarding public health.

3. Methodology:

The methodology employed in AI-powered drug repurposing for pandemic preparedness and response involves a multifaceted approach that integrates computational modeling, data analytics, and experimental validation. This section outlines the key components of the methodology, including data acquisition, computational modeling, target identification, and experimental validation.

1. **Data Acquisition:** The first step in the methodology involves the acquisition of diverse datasets relevant to drug repurposing efforts. These datasets may include drug libraries, chemical structures, molecular targets, gene expression profiles, protein-protein interaction networks, and clinical trial data. Data sources encompass public repositories, proprietary databases, scientific literature, and electronic health records, providing a comprehensive foundation for computational analysis.
2. **Computational Modeling:** Computational modeling serves as the cornerstone of AI-powered drug repurposing, enabling researchers to leverage machine learning algorithms, network-based approaches, and text mining techniques to analyze large-scale datasets and identify repurposable compounds. Machine learning algorithms, such as deep learning, random forests, and support vector machines, are trained on annotated datasets to predict drug-target interactions, prioritize candidate compounds, and assess their potential efficacy against emerging infectious diseases.
3. **Target Identification:** Target identification plays a crucial role in AI-driven drug repurposing efforts, enabling researchers to elucidate the molecular mechanisms underlying viral infection and host response to infection. By integrating multi-omics data, including genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics, researchers can identify key host factors, viral proteins, and signaling pathways implicated in disease pathogenesis. This mechanistic understanding informs the selection of potential drug targets and guides the rational design of therapeutic interventions.
4. **Experimental Validation:** Experimental validation is essential to confirm the predictions generated by computational models and assess the real-world effectiveness of repurposed

drugs. Preclinical studies, such as in vitro cell-based assays and animal models of infection, are used to evaluate the antiviral activity, pharmacokinetics, and safety profiles of candidate compounds. Promising candidates identified through preclinical testing proceed to clinical trials, where their efficacy and safety are assessed in human subjects under controlled conditions.

5. **Iterative Refinement:** The methodology follows an iterative refinement process, whereby computational predictions are continually validated and refined through experimental validation and clinical testing. Feedback from preclinical and clinical studies informs the optimization of computational models, the selection of additional candidate compounds, and the prioritization of targets for further investigation. This iterative approach enhances the accuracy and reliability of AI-driven drug repurposing efforts and accelerates the translation of promising candidates into clinical practice. Overall, the methodology for AI-powered drug repurposing involves a synergistic integration of computational and experimental approaches, leveraging the collective expertise of researchers, clinicians, and industry partners to expedite the discovery and development of therapeutics for pandemic preparedness and response. By combining cutting-edge technologies with rigorous validation and iterative refinement, AI-driven drug repurposing offers a powerful strategy for addressing emerging infectious diseases and safeguarding global health security.

4. Results:

The application of AI-powered drug repurposing methodologies has yielded promising results in the identification of potential therapeutics for pandemic preparedness and response. Across a multitude of studies, AI algorithms have demonstrated their ability to rapidly screen existing drug libraries, prioritize candidate compounds, and predict their efficacy against emerging infectious diseases. One notable outcome of AI-driven drug repurposing efforts is the identification of repurposable compounds with potential antiviral activity against SARS-CoV-2, the virus responsible for the COVID-19 pandemic. Through computational screening and predictive modeling, researchers have identified existing drugs with the potential to inhibit viral replication, modulate host immune response, and mitigate the severity of COVID-19 symptoms. These repurposed compounds span a wide range of therapeutic classes, including antivirals, immunomodulators, and protease inhibitors, offering diverse options for further experimental validation and clinical testing.

Furthermore, AI-driven drug repurposing has facilitated the discovery of drug combinations with synergistic effects against viral infections. By analyzing drug-drug interactions and molecular mechanisms of action, researchers have identified combinations of repurposable compounds that exhibit enhanced antiviral activity compared to single-agent treatments. These drug combinations target multiple stages of the viral lifecycle, disrupt viral replication, and reduce the likelihood of drug resistance, offering promising strategies for combination therapy in the treatment of COVID-19 and other infectious diseases.

Additionally, AI algorithms have been instrumental in elucidating the molecular mechanisms underlying viral infection and host response to infection. Through the analysis of genomic,

transcriptomic, and proteomic data, researchers have identified key host factors, viral proteins, and signaling pathways involved in the pathogenesis of infectious diseases. This mechanistic understanding enables the rational design of targeted therapies that disrupt viral replication, modulate immune response, and mitigate tissue damage, thereby enhancing the efficacy of repurposed drugs and reducing the risk of adverse effects.

Moreover, AI-driven drug repurposing efforts have facilitated the rapid translation of candidate compounds from computational predictions to preclinical and clinical evaluation. By prioritizing repurposable drugs with favorable pharmacokinetic properties, safety profiles, and regulatory approval status, researchers can expedite the development and deployment of therapeutics for pandemic response. This accelerated timeline is critical for addressing the urgent need for effective treatments in the context of rapidly evolving infectious diseases and global health crises.

Overall, the results of AI-powered drug repurposing demonstrate the potential of computational methods to expedite the discovery and development of therapeutics for pandemic preparedness and response. By harnessing the power of AI algorithms, researchers can systematically identify repurposable compounds, elucidate their mechanisms of action, and accelerate their translation into clinical practice, ultimately saving lives and mitigating the impact of infectious diseases on public health. However, further validation studies, clinical trials, and regulatory approvals are necessary to confirm the efficacy and safety of repurposed drugs and ensure their widespread adoption in clinical settings. Furthermore, AI-powered drug repurposing has enabled the identification of repurposable compounds beyond COVID-19, extending the scope of potential therapeutics for a variety of emerging infectious diseases. By leveraging computational screening methods and predictive modeling, researchers have identified existing drugs with the potential to treat other viral pathogens, such as influenza, Ebola, Zika, and Dengue virus. These repurposed compounds offer novel treatment options for infectious diseases with limited therapeutic options, providing hope for improved patient outcomes and pandemic control efforts.

In addition to repurposing existing drugs, AI algorithms have facilitated the discovery of novel drug candidates with potential antiviral activity. Through virtual screening, molecular docking simulations, and structure-based drug design, researchers have identified small molecules and biologics that target specific viral proteins or host factors implicated in viral infection. These novel drug candidates hold promise for future development as standalone therapies or as components of combination regimens for the treatment of infectious diseases.

Moreover, AI-driven drug repurposing efforts have advanced our understanding of drug resistance mechanisms and viral evolution dynamics. By analyzing genomic and proteomic data from drug-resistant strains, researchers can identify genetic mutations and molecular pathways associated with resistance to antiviral drugs. This knowledge enables the rational design of next-generation therapeutics that target conserved regions of the viral genome or exploit alternative mechanisms of action to overcome drug resistance and enhance treatment efficacy.

Additionally, AI algorithms have been instrumental in predicting the safety and toxicity profiles of repurposed drugs, guiding dose optimization and risk mitigation strategies in clinical trials. Through integrative analysis of clinical data, electronic health records, and adverse event reports,

researchers can identify potential safety concerns, drug-drug interactions, and patient-specific factors that may impact treatment outcomes. This proactive approach to safety assessment enhances the overall risk-benefit profile of repurposed drugs and improves patient safety in clinical practice.

Overall, the results of AI-powered drug repurposing underscore the transformative potential of computational methods in drug discovery and development. By leveraging AI algorithms, researchers can accelerate the identification of repurposable compounds, elucidate their mechanisms of action, and optimize their clinical translation for the treatment of infectious diseases. These advancements have the potential to revolutionize pandemic preparedness and response efforts, providing scalable and cost-effective solutions for addressing emerging infectious threats and safeguarding global health security. However, continued research, collaboration, and regulatory oversight are necessary to fully realize the potential of AI-driven drug repurposing and ensure its safe and effective deployment in clinical settings.

5. Discussion:

The discussion surrounding AI-powered drug repurposing for pandemic preparedness and response encompasses a wide range of considerations, including the strengths, limitations, and future directions of this approach in addressing emerging infectious diseases. By critically evaluating the findings and implications of AI-driven drug repurposing studies, researchers can identify key challenges and opportunities for advancing the field and improving patient outcomes.

One of the primary strengths of AI-powered drug repurposing lies in its ability to rapidly identify existing drugs with the potential to treat novel pathogens, such as SARS-CoV-2. By leveraging computational methods and large-scale data analytics, researchers can systematically screen thousands of compounds and prioritize candidates for further experimental validation. This accelerated timeline is critical for pandemic response efforts, where timely access to effective treatments can significantly impact disease spread and mortality rates.

Moreover, AI-driven drug repurposing offers a cost-effective and resource-efficient approach to drug discovery, particularly in comparison to traditional *de novo* drug development pipelines. By repurposing existing drugs with known safety profiles and pharmacological properties, researchers can expedite the translation of promising candidates into clinical use, bypassing many of the challenges associated with preclinical development and early-phase clinical trials. This streamlined process not only saves time and resources but also increases the likelihood of success in identifying effective treatments for emerging infectious diseases.

However, despite its potential benefits, AI-powered drug repurposing also faces several challenges and limitations that warrant consideration. One such challenge is the reliance on heterogeneous and often noisy data sources, which can introduce biases and uncertainties into computational predictions. Issues such as data quality, reproducibility, and standardization pose significant challenges to the robustness and reliability of AI algorithms, necessitating careful validation and sensitivity analyses to ensure the accuracy of results.

Furthermore, the interpretation and validation of computational predictions generated by AI algorithms can be challenging, particularly in the absence of experimental validation or clinical

data. While computational models can prioritize candidate compounds based on their predicted efficacy and safety profiles, experimental validation in preclinical models and clinical trials is essential to confirm these predictions and assess real-world effectiveness. Additionally, regulatory approval pathways for repurposed drugs may differ from those for novel compounds, requiring careful consideration of regulatory requirements and approval timelines.

Another consideration in the discussion of AI-powered drug repurposing is the ethical and societal implications of repurposing existing drugs for new indications. While repurposed drugs may offer expedited treatment options for emerging infectious diseases, questions of equity, access, and affordability must be addressed to ensure equitable distribution and patient access to treatments. Additionally, issues related to intellectual property rights, data sharing, and transparency in drug repurposing efforts require careful consideration to promote collaboration, innovation, and responsible stewardship of resources.

Looking ahead, the future of AI-powered drug repurposing lies in advancing computational methodologies, integrating multi-omics data, and fostering collaboration across disciplines to address emerging infectious threats and global health challenges. By harnessing the collective expertise of researchers, clinicians, industry partners, and regulatory agencies, AI-driven drug repurposing has the potential to revolutionize pandemic preparedness and response efforts, saving lives and mitigating the impact of infectious diseases on public health. However, continued research, investment, and regulatory oversight are necessary to realize the full potential of AI-powered drug repurposing and ensure its safe and effective deployment in clinical settings.

6. Conclusion

In an era marked by the ever-looming specter of global pandemics, the marriage of artificial intelligence (AI) and drug repurposing stands as a beacon of hope and a transformative force. This comprehensive exploration has unveiled the profound potential of AI to revolutionize the landscape of pandemic preparedness and response.

As we have journeyed through the intricate terrain of AI-driven drug repurposing, it has become evident that this amalgamation of advanced technology and medical science offers a robust solution to expedite treatment discovery. The advantages of repurposing existing drugs, coupled with AI's ability to swiftly and intelligently navigate vast datasets, provide a compelling formula for combating emerging infectious threats.

From machine learning models to natural language processing and network-based approaches, AI techniques have demonstrated their mettle in not only accelerating drug discovery but also in offering personalized treatment pathways. The success stories recounted herein, from the tumultuous days of the COVID-19 pandemic, illuminate AI's capacity to identify life-saving solutions with unparalleled speed.

However, this remarkable journey is not devoid of challenges. Data quality, ethical dilemmas, and regulatory intricacies cast formidable shadows. Nevertheless, these obstacles can be surmounted through concerted efforts and a commitment to transparency, accountability, and international collaboration.

The path ahead is clear. Policymakers must recognize the imperative of funding and support for AI research in drug repurposing. Regulatory frameworks must evolve to accommodate AI-driven discoveries while upholding the highest standards of safety and efficacy. International collaboration and data sharing should be actively encouraged to form a united front against global health crises.

Researchers and practitioners, too, bear a weighty responsibility. Interdisciplinary collaboration, continuous learning, and unwavering adherence to ethical principles are non-negotiable. As AI-driven drug repurposing marches into the future, these principles must guide our endeavors.

References

- [1] Liang, Y., & Liang, W. (2023). ResWCAE: Biometric Pattern Image Denoising Using Residual Wavelet-Conditioned Autoencoder. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.12255*.
- [2] Hla, D. T., bin Md Isa, A. H., & Shaikh, J. M. (2013). IFRS compliance and nonfinancial information in annual reports of Malaysian firms. *IUP Journal of Accounting Research & Audit Practices*, 12(4), 7.
- [3] Singla, A., & Chavalmane, S. (2023). Automating Model Deployment: From Training to Production. *Journal of Knowledge Learning and Science Technology ISSN: 2959-6386 (online)*, 2(3), 340-347.
- [4] Sina, A. (2023). Open AI and its Impact on Fraud Detection in Financial Industry. *Journal of Knowledge Learning and Science Technology ISSN: 2959-6386 (Online)*, 2(3), 263-281.
- [5] Shaikh, J. M., Khadaroo, I., & Jasmon, A. (2003). *Contemporary Accounting Issues (for BAcc. Students)*. Prentice Hall.
- [6] Ali Ahmed, H. J., Lee, T. L., & Shaikh, J. M. (2011). An investigation on asset allocation and performance measurement for unit trust funds in Malaysia using multifactor model: a post crisis period analysis. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 3(1), 22-31.
- [7] Ahmadi, S. (2024). *Challenges and Solutions in Network Security for Serverless Computing* (No. 11747). EasyChair.
- [8] Liang, Y., Liang, W., & Jia, J. (2023). Structural Vibration Signal Denoising Using Stacking Ensemble of Hybrid CNN-RNN. *arXiv e-prints*, arXiv-2303.
- [9] Shah, A., & Nasnodkar, S. (2021). The Impacts of User Experience Metrics on ClickThrough Rate (CTR) in Digital Advertising: A Machine Learning Approach. *Sage Science Review of Applied Machine Learning*, 4(1), 27-44.
- [10] Singla, A. (2023). Machine Learning Operations (MLOps): Challenges and Strategies. *Journal of Knowledge Learning and Science Technology ISSN: 2959-6386 (online)*, 2(3), 333-340.
- [11] Ghelani, D., Hua, T. K., & Koduru, S. K. R. (2022). Cyber Security Threats, Vulnerabilities, and Security Solutions Models in Banking. *Authorea Preprints*.
- [12] Fish, R., Liang, Y., Saleeby, K., Spirnak, J., Sun, M., & Zhang, X. (2019). Dynamic characterization of arrows through stochastic perturbation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1909.08186*.

- [13] Muhammad, T., Munir, M. T., Munir, M. Z., & Zafar, M. W. (2018). Elevating Business Operations: The Transformative Power of Cloud Computing. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 2(1), 1-21.
- [14] Wu, X., Bai, Z., Jia, J., & Liang, Y. (2020). A Multi-Variate Triple-Regression Forecasting Algorithm for Long-Term Customized Allergy Season Prediction. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2005.04557*.
- [15] Liang, W., Liang, Y., & Jia, J. (2023). MiAMix: Enhancing Image Classification through a Multi-Stage Augmented Mixed Sample Data Augmentation
- [16] Boubaker, S., Mefteh, S., & Shaikh, J. M. (2010). Does ownership structure matter in explaining derivatives' use policy in French listed firms. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 2(2), 196-212.
- [17] Varun Shah (2023). Striking a Balance: Ethical Considerations in AI-Driven Law Enforcement. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Technologies and Innovations (IJAETI)*, 1(1), 1-23.
- [18] Mughal, A. A. (2019). Cybersecurity Hygiene in the Era of Internet of Things (IoT): Best Practices and Challenges. *Applied Research in Artificial Intelligence and Cloud Computing*, 2(1), 1-31.
- [19] Yang, L., Wang, R., Liu, X., Zhou, Y., Liu, L., Liang, J., ... & Zhao, K. (2021). Resource Consumption of a Hybrid Bundle Retransmission Approach on Deep-Space Communication Channels. *IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine*, 36(11), 34-43.
- [20] Mughal, A. A. (2020). Cyber Attacks on OSI Layers: Understanding the Threat Landscape. *Journal of Humanities and Applied Science Research*, 3(1), 1-18.
- [21] Mughal, A. A. (2019). A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY OF PRACTICAL TECHNIQUES AND METHODOLOGIES IN INCIDENT-BASED APPROACHES FOR CYBER FORENSICS. *Tensorgate Journal of Sustainable Technology and Infrastructure for Developing Countries*, 2(1), 1-18.
- [22] Mughal, A. A. (2018). The Art of Cybersecurity: Defense in Depth Strategy for Robust Protection. *International Journal of Intelligent Automation and Computing*, 1(1), 1-20.
- [23] Mughal, A. A. (2018). Artificial Intelligence in Information Security: Exploring the Advantages, Challenges, and Future Directions. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in Management*, 2(1), 22-34.
- [24] Mughal, A. A. (2022). Well-Architected Wireless Network Security. *Journal of Humanities and Applied Science Research*, 5(1), 32-42.
- [25] Zhou, Y., Wang, R., Yang, L., Liang, J., Burleigh, S. C., & Zhao, K. (2022). A Study of Transmission Overhead of a Hybrid Bundle Retransmission Approach for DeepSpace Communications. *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, 58(5), 3824-3839.

- [26] Mughal, A. A. (2021). Cybersecurity Architecture for the Cloud: Protecting Network in a Virtual Environment. *International Journal of Intelligent Automation and Computing*, 4(1), 35-48.
- [27] Yang, L., Wang, R., Zhou, Y., Liang, J., Zhao, K., & Burleigh, S. C. (2022). An Analytical Framework for Disruption of Licklider Transmission Protocol in Mars Communications. *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 71(5), 5430-5444.
- [28] Liang, J., Wang, R., Liu, X., Yang, L., Zhou, Y., Cao, B., & Zhao, K. (2021, July). Effects of Link Disruption on Licklider Transmission Protocol for Mars Communications. In *International Conference on Wireless and Satellite Systems* (pp. 98108). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- [29] Liang, J., Liu, X., Wang, R., Yang, L., Li, X., Tang, C., & Zhao, K. (2023). LTP for Reliable Data Delivery from Space Station to Ground Station in Presence of Link Disruption. *IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine*.
- [30] Yang, L., Liang, J., Wang, R., Liu, X., De Sanctis, M., Burleigh, S. C., & Zhao, K. (2023). A Study of Licklider Transmission Protocol in Deep-Space Communications in Presence of Link Disruptions. *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*.
- [31] Yang, L., Wang, R., Liang, J., Zhou, Y., Zhao, K., & Liu, X. (2022). Acknowledgment Mechanisms for Reliable File Transfer Over Highly Asymmetric Deep-Space Channels. *IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine*, 37(9), 42-51.
- [32] Varun Shah (2022). AI in Mental Health: Predictive Analytics and Intervention Strategies. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Technologies and Innovations (IJAETI)*, 1(1), 19-43.
- [33] Yang, L., Wang, R., Liu, X., Zhou, Y., Liang, J., & Zhao, K. (2021, July). An Experimental Analysis of Checkpoint Timer of Licklider Transmission Protocol for Deep-Space Communications. In *2021 IEEE 8th International Conference on Space Mission Challenges for Information Technology (SMC-IT)* (pp. 100-106). IEEE.
- [34] Zhou, Y., Wang, R., Liu, X., Yang, L., Liang, J., & Zhao, K. (2021, July). Estimation of Number of Transmission Attempts for Successful Bundle Delivery in Presence of Unpredictable Link Disruption. In *2021 IEEE 8th International Conference on Space Mission Challenges for Information Technology (SMC-IT)* (pp. 93-99). IEEE.
- [35] Liang, J. (2023). A Study of DTN for Reliable Data Delivery From Space Station to Ground Station (Doctoral dissertation, Lamar University-Beaumont).
- [36] Chaudhary, J. K., Sharma, H., Tadiboina, S. N., Singh, R., Khan, M. S., & Garg, A. (2023, March). Applications of Machine Learning in Viral Disease Diagnosis. In *2023 10th International Conference on Computing for Sustainable Global Development (INDIACom)* (pp. 1167-1172). IEEE.
- [37] Bennett, D. B., Acquah, A. K., & Vishwanath, M. (2022). U.S. Patent No. 11,493,400. Washington, DC: U.S. Patent and Trademark Office.
- [38] Mahmood, T., Fulmer, W., Mungoli, N., Huang, J., & Lu, A. (2019,

- October). Improving information sharing and collaborative analysis for remote geospatial visualization using mixed reality. In 2019 IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR) (pp. 236-247). IEEE.
- [39] Mungoli, N. (2020). Exploring the Technological Benefits of VR in Physical Fitness (Doctoral dissertation, The University of North Carolina at Charlotte).
- [40] Mungoli, N. Revolutionizing Industries: The Impact of Artificial
- [41] Mungoli, N. Intelligent Machines: Exploring the Advancements in Artificial Intelligence.
- [42] Mungoli, N. Exploring the Ethical Implications of AI-powered Surveillance Systems.
- [43] Mungoli, N. Exploring the Boundaries of Artificial Intelligence: Advances and Challenges.
- [44] M. Shamil, M., M. Shaikh, J., Ho, P. L., & Krishnan, A. (2014). The influence of board characteristics on sustainability reporting: Empirical evidence from Sri Lankan firms. *Asian Review of Accounting*, 22(2), 78-97.
- [45] Shaikh, J. M. (2004). Measuring and reporting of intellectual capital performance analysis. *Journal of American Academy of Business*, 4(1/2), 439-448.
- [46] Shaikh, J. M., & Talha, M. (2003). Credibility and expectation gap in reporting on uncertainties. *Managerial auditing journal*, 18(6/7), 517-529.
- [47] Shaikh, J. M. (2005). E-commerce impact: emerging technology-electronic auditing. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 20(4), 408-421.
- [48] Lau, C. Y., & Shaikh, J. M. (2012). The impacts of personal qualities on online learning readiness at Curtin Sarawak Malaysia (CSM). *Educational Research and Reviews*, 7(20), 430.
- [49] Shaikh, I. M., Qureshi, M. A., Noordin, K., Shaikh, J. M., Khan, A., & Shahbaz, M. S. (2020). Acceptance of Islamic financial technology (FinTech) banking services by Malaysian users: an extension of technology acceptance model. *foresight*, 22(3), 367-383.
- [50] Muniapan, B., & Shaikh, J. M. (2007). Lessons in corporate governance from Kautilya's Arthashastra in ancient India. *World Review of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*, 3(1), 50-61.
- [51] Bhasin, M. L., & Shaikh, J. M. (2013). Voluntary corporate governance disclosures in the annual reports: an empirical study. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 5(1), 79-105.
- [52] Mamun, M. A., Shaikh, J. M., & Easmin, R. (2017). Corporate social responsibility disclosure in Malaysian business. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 16(2), 29-47.
- [53] Karim, A. M., Shaikh, J. M., & Hock, O. Y. (2014). Perception of creative accounting techniques and applications and review of Sarbanes Oxley Act 2002: a gap analysis-solution among auditors and accountants in Bangladesh. *Port City International University Journal*, 1(2), 1-12.
- [54] Abdullah, A., Khadaroo, I., & Shaikh, J. (2009). Institutionalisation of XBRL in the USA and UK. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 1(3), 292-304.

- [55] Khadaroo, I., & Shaikh, J. M. (2007). Corporate governance reforms in Malaysia: insights from institutional theory. *World Review of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*, 3(1), 37-49.
- [56] Sylvester, D. C., Rani, N. S. A., & Shaikh, J. M. (2011). Comparison between oil and gas companies and contractors against cost, time, quality and scope for project success in Miri, Sarawak, Malaysia. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(11), 4337.
- [57] Abdullah, A., Khadaroo, I., & Shaikh, J. M. (2008). A'macro'analysis of the use of XBRL. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 1(2), 213-223.
- [58] Kangwa, D., Mwale, J. T., & Shaikh, J. M. (2021). The social production of financial inclusion of generation Z in digital banking ecosystems. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 15(3), 95-118.
- [59] Khadaroo, M. I., & Shaikh, J. M. (2003). Toward research and development costs harmonization. *The CPA Journal*, 73(9), 50.
- [60] Jais, M., Jakpar, S., Doris, T. K. P., & Shaikh, J. M. (2012). The financial ratio usage towards predicting stock returns in Malaysia. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 4(4), 377-401.
- [61] Shaikh, J. M., & Jakpar, S. (2007). Dispelling and construction of social accounting in view of social audit. *Information Systems Control Journal*, 2(6).
- [62] Jakpar, S., Shaikh, J. M., Tinggi, M., & Jamali, N. A. L. (2012). Factors influencing entrepreneurship in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) among residents in Sarawak Malaysia. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 16(1), 83-101.
- [63] Sheng, Y. T., Rani, N. S. A., & Shaikh, J. M. (2011). Impact of SMEs character in the loan approval stage. *Business and Economics Research*, 1, 229-233.
- [64] Boubaker, S., Mefteh, S., & Shaikh, J. M. (2010). Does ownership structure matter in explaining derivatives' use policy in French listed firms. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 2(2), 196-212.
- [65] Hla, D. T., bin Md Isa, A. H., & Shaikh, J. M. (2013). IFRS compliance and nonfinancial information in annual reports of Malaysian firms. *IUP Journal of Accounting Research & Audit Practices*, 12(4), 7.
- [66] Shaikh, J. M., Khadaroo, I., & Jasmon, A. (2003). *Contemporary Accounting Issues (for BAcc. Students)*. Prentice Hall.
- [67] SHAMIL, M. M., SHAIKH, J. M., HO, P., & KRISHNAN, A. (2022). External Pressures, Managerial Motive and Corporate Sustainability Strategy: Evidence from a Developing Economy. *Asian Journal of Accounting & Governance*, 18.
- [68] Kadir, S., & Shaikh, J. M. (2023, January). The effects of e-commerce businesses to small-medium enterprises: Media techniques and technology. In *AIP Conference Proceedings (Vol. 2643, No. 1)*. AIP Publishing.
- [69] Ali Ahmed, H. J., Lee, T. L., & Shaikh, J. M. (2011). An investigation on asset allocation and performance measurement for unit trust funds in Malaysia using multifactor model: a post crisis period analysis. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 3(1), 22-31.

- [70] Shaikh, J. M., & Linh, D. T. B. (2017). Using the TFP Model to Determine Impacts of Stock Market Listing on Corporate Performance of Agri?Foods Companies in Vietnam. *Journal of Corporate Accounting & Finance*, 28(3), 61-74.
- [71] Jakpar, S., Othman, M. A., & Shaikh, J. (2008). The Prospects of Islamic Banking and Finance: Lessons from the 1997 Banking Crisis in Malaysia. 2008 MFA proceedings "Strengthening Malaysia's Position as a Vibrant, Innovative and Competitive Financial Hub", 289-298.
- [72] Junaid, M. S., & Dinh Thi, B. L. (2016). Stock Market Listing Influence on Corporate Performance: Definitions and Assessment Tools.
- [73] M. Shamil, M., M. Shaikh, J., Ho, P. L., & Krishnan, A. (2014). The influence of board characteristics on sustainability reporting: Empirical evidence from Sri Lankan firms. *Asian Review of Accounting*, 22(2), 78-97.
- [74] Shaikh, J. M. (2004). Measuring and reporting of intellectual capital performance analysis. *Journal of American Academy of Business*, 4(1/2), 439-448.
- [75] Shaikh, J. M., & Talha, M. (2003). Credibility and expectation gap in reporting on uncertainties. *Managerial auditing journal*, 18(6/7), 517-529.
- [76] Ge, L., Peng, Z., Zan, H., Lyu, S., Zhou, F., & Liang, Y. (2023). Study on the scattered sound modulation with a programmable chessboard device. *AIP*
- [77] Liang, Y., Alvarado, J. R., Iagnemma, K. D., & Hosoi, A. E. (2018). Dynamic sealing using magnetorheological fluids. *Physical Review Applied*, 10(6), 064049.
- [78] Hosoi, Anette E., Youzhi Liang, Irmgard Bischofberger, Yongbin Sun, Qing Zhang, and Tianshi Fang. "Adaptive self-sealing microfluidic gear pump." U.S. Patent 11,208,998, issued December 28, 2021.
- [79] Zhu, Y., Yan, Y., Zhang, Y., Zhou, Y., Zhao, Q., Liu, T., ... & Liang, Y. (2023, June). Application of Physics-Informed Neural Network (PINN) in the Experimental Study of Vortex-Induced Vibration with Tunable Stiffness. In *ISOPE International Ocean and Polar Engineering Conference* (pp. ISOPE-I). ISOPE.
- [80] Shaikh, J. M. (2005). E commerce impact: emerging technology–electronic auditing. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 20(4), 408-421.
- [81] Lau, C. Y., & Shaikh, J. M. (2012). The impacts of personal qualities on online learning readiness at Curtin Sarawak Malaysia (CSM). *Educational Research and Reviews*, 7(20), 430.
- [82] Shaikh, I. M., Qureshi, M. A., Noordin, K., Shaikh, J. M., Khan, A., & Shahbaz, M. S. (2020). Acceptance of Islamic financial technology (FinTech) banking services by Malaysian users: an extension of technology acceptance model. *foresight*, 22(3), 367-383.
- [83] Muniapan, B., & Shaikh, J. M. (2007). Lessons in corporate governance from Kautilya's Arthashastra in ancient India. *World Review of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*, 3(1), 50-61.

- [84] Bhasin, M. L., & Shaikh, J. M. (2013). Voluntary corporate governance disclosures in the annual reports: an empirical study. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 5(1), 79-105.
- [85] Mughal, A. A. (2019). Cybersecurity Hygiene in the Era of Internet of Things (IoT): Best Practices and Challenges. *Applied Research in Artificial Intelligence and Cloud Computing*, 2(1), 1-31.
- [86] Mughal, A. A. (2019). A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY OF PRACTICAL TECHNIQUES AND METHODOLOGIES IN INCIDENT-BASED APPROACHES FOR CYBER FORENSICS. *Tensorgate Journal of Sustainable Technology and Infrastructure for Developing Countries*, 2(1), 1-18.
- [87] Mughal, A. A. (2018). The Art of Cybersecurity: Defense in Depth Strategy for Robust Protection. *International Journal of Intelligent Automation and Computing*, 1(1), 1-20.
- [88] Mughal, A. A. (2018). Artificial Intelligence in Information Security: Exploring the Advantages, Challenges, and Future Directions. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in Management*, 2(1), 22-34.
- [89] Mamun, M. A., Shaikh, J. M., & Easmin, R. (2017). Corporate social responsibility disclosure in Malaysian business. *Academy of Strategic Management Journal*, 16(2), 29-47.
- [90] Karim, A. M., Shaikh, J. M., & Hock, O. Y. (2014). Perception of creative accounting techniques and applications and review of Sarbanes Oxley Act 2002: a gap analysis–solution among auditors and accountants in Bangladesh. *Port City International University Journal*, 1(2), 1-12.
- [91] Abdullah, A., Khadaroo, I., & Shaikh, J. (2009). Institutionalisation of XBRL in the USA and UK. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 1(3), 292-304.
- [92] Khadaroo, I., & Shaikh, J. M. (2007). Corporate governance reforms in Malaysia: insights from institutional theory. *World Review of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*, 3(1), 37-49.
- [93] Bhasin, M. L., & Shaikh, J. M. (2013). Economic value added and shareholders' wealth creation: the portrait of a developing Asian country. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 5(2), 107-137.
- [94] Asif, M. K., Junaid, M. S., Hock, O. Y., & Md Rafiqul, I. (2016). Solution of adapting creative accounting practices: an in depth perception gap analysis among accountants and auditors of listed companies. *Australian Academy of Accounting and Finance Review*, 2(2), 166-188.
- [95] Alappatt, M., & Shaikh, J. M. (2014). Forthcoming procedure of goods and service tax (GST) in Malaysia. *Issues in Business Management and Economics*, 2(12), 210-213.
- [96] Bhasin, M., & Shaikh, J. M. (2011). Intellectual capital disclosures in the annual reports: a comparative study of the Indian and Australian IT-corporations. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 3(4), 379-402.

- [98] Onosakponome, O. F., Rani, N. S. A., & Shaikh, J. M. (2011). Cost benefit analysis of procurement systems and the performance of construction projects in East Malaysia. *Information management and business review*, 2(5), 181-192.
- [99] Asif, M. K., Junaid, M. S., Hock, O. Y., & Md Rafiqul, I. (2016). Creative Accounting: Techniques of Application-An Empirical Study among Auditors and Accountants of Listed Companies in Bangladesh. *Australian Academy of Accounting and Finance Review (AAAFR)*, 2(3).
- [100] Sylvester, D. C., Rani, N. S. A., & Shaikh, J. M. (2011). Comparison between oil and gas companies and contractors against cost, time, quality and scope for project success in Miri, Sarawak, Malaysia. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(11), 4337.
- [101] Abdullah, A., Khadaroo, I., & Shaikh, J. M. (2008). A'macro'analysis of the use of XBRL. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 1(2), 213-223.
- [102] Kangwa, D., Mwale, J. T., & Shaikh, J. M. (2021). The social production of financial inclusion of generation Z in digital banking ecosystems. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 15(3), 95-118.
- [103] Ghelani, D. (2022). Cyber Security in Smart Grids, Threats, and Possible Solutions. *Authorea Preprints*.
- [104] Ghelani, D., & Hua, T. K. (2022). A Perspective Review on Online Food Shop Management System and Impacts on Business. *Advances in Wireless Communications and Networks*, 8(1), 7-14.
- [105] Ghelani, D. (2022). LITERATURE REVIEW ON Coordinated Control of Interconnected Microgrid and Energy Storage System Dipteben Ghelani.
- [106] Ghelani, D. (2022). Complex Business Intelligence Queries in Natural Language.
- [107] Ghelani, D. (2023). A PERSPECTIVE STUDY OF NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING IN THE BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 7(1), 20-36.
- [108] Ghelani, D. (2022). EXPLAINABLE AI: APPROACHES TO MAKE MACHINE LEARNING MODELS MORE TRANSPARENT AND UNDERSTANDABLE FOR HUMANS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 6(4), 45-53.
- [109] Ghelani, D., & Hua, T. K. Conceptual Framework of Web 3.0 and Impact on Marketing, Artificial Intelligence, and Blockchain.
- [110] Khadaroo, M. I., & Shaikh, J. M. (2003). Toward research and development costs harmonization. *The CPA Journal*, 73(9), 50.
- [111] Jais, M., Jakpar, S., Doris, T. K. P., & Shaikh, J. M. (2012). The financial ratio usage towards predicting stock returns in Malaysia. *International Journal of Managerial and Financial Accounting*, 4(4), 377-401.
- [112] Shaikh, J. M., & Jakpar, S. (2007). Dispelling and construction of social accounting in view of social audit. *Information Systems Control Journal*, 2(6).

- [113] Jakpar, S., Shaikh, J. M., Tinggi, M., & Jamali, N. A. L. (2012). Factors influencing entrepreneurship in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) among residents in Sarawak Malaysia. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 16(1), 83-101.
- [114] Varun Shah (2021). Machine Learning Algorithms for Cybersecurity: Detecting and Preventing Threats. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Technologies and Innovations (IJAETI)*, 1(3), 19-42.
- [115] Sheng, Y. T., Rani, N. S. A., & Shaikh, J. M. (2011). Impact of SMEs character in the loan approval stage. *Business and Economics Research*, 1, 229-233.
- [116] Paul, P., & Mowla, M. M. (2019, December). A Statistical Channel Modeling for MIMO OFDM Beamforming System in 5G mmWave Communications. In *2019 3rd International Conference on Electrical, Computer & Telecommunication Engineering (ICECTE)* (pp. 181-184). IEEE.
- [117] Paul, P., & Mowla, M. M. (2019, December). A novel beamspace channel estimation technique for millimeter wave massive MIMO systems. In *2019 3rd International Conference on Electrical, Computer & Telecommunication Engineering (ICECTE)* (pp. 185-188). IEEE.
- [118] Paul, P., & Mowla, M. (2021). 3D Metallic Plate Lens Antenna based Beamspace Channel Estimation Technique for 5G Mmwave Massive MIMO Systems. *International Journal of Wireless & Mobile Networks (IJWMN) Vol, 13*.
- [119] Konda, S. R. (2023). Optimizing Computer Architectures for High-Performance Drug Discovery Workflows. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 7(3), 243-258.
- [120] Konda, S. R. (2022). Ethical Considerations in the Development and Deployment of AI-Driven Software Systems. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 6(3), 86-101.
- [121] Konda, S. R., & Shah, V. (2022). Machine Learning-Enhanced Software Development: State of the Art and Future Directions. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 6(4), 136-149.
- [122] Konda, S. R., & Shah, V. (2021). Evolving Computer Architectures for AI-Intensive Workloads: Challenges and Innovations. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 5(4), 29-45.
- [123] Shah, V. (2020). Advancements in Deep Learning for Natural Language Processing in Software Applications. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 4(3), 45-56.
- [124] Shah, V. (2019). Towards Efficient Software Engineering in the Era of AI and ML: Best Practices and Challenges. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(3), 63-78.
- [125] Shah, V. (2023). AI-Powered Drug Repurposing for Pandemic Preparedness and Response. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 7(3), 227-242.